

1 **Gold-standard local validation enhances interpretability of** 2 **cryo-EM maps**

3 J. Vargas^{1,2*}, A. V. Florea¹, S. Pellegrino³, J. Burguet-Castell⁴, J. A. Gómez-Pedrero², G. Arruda Bezerra³,
4 K. H. Bui⁵,

5 *¹Macromolecular Structures Department, Centro Nacional de Biotecnología-CSIC*

6 *C/ Darwin 3, 28049 Cantoblanco, Madrid, Spain*

7 *²Departamento de Óptica, Universidad Complutense de Madrid*

8 *Madrid, 28040, Spain*

9 *³Bicycle Therapeutics, Portway Building, Granta Park, Cambridge CB21 6GS, United Kingdom,*

10 *University of Oxford, Oxford OX3 7FZ, U.K.*

11 *⁴Departamento de Sistemas Informáticos, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid*

12 *Madrid, 28223, Spain*

13 *⁵Department of Anatomy and Cell Biology, McGill University*

14 *3640 Rue University, Montréal, QC H3A 0C7, Canada*

15 **Correspondence to jvargas@ucm.es; javier.vargas@cnb.csic.es*

16 **Abstract**

17 Accurate interpretation of cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM) maps requires robust local
18 measures of quality and resolution. Current approaches are often limited by single-map estimates,
19 user-defined solvent masks that risk bias and overfitting, and an exclusive reliance on signal
20 amplitudes while neglecting phase information. Here, we present a Gold-standard framework
21 requiring minimal user intervention for local validation and enhancement of cryo-EM
22 reconstructions that addresses these limitations by jointly analyzing amplitudes and phases
23 between independent half-maps or between maps and atomic models. All methods are computed

24 voxel-wise in real space from independent half-maps, ensuring unbiased local evaluation. The
25 toolbox includes unbiased local sharpening (LocSpiral2), per-voxel figure-of-merit, signal-to-
26 noise estimation and general quality assessment (LocFOM, LocSNR and LocQ), directional local
27 anisotropy evaluation (LocAnisotropy) and Gold-standard local resolution mapping
28 (LocResMap). Together, these approaches provide a comprehensive and unified strategy for
29 evaluating cryo-EM maps at the voxel level, improving interpretability and offering more reliable
30 guidance for atomic modelling. Applications to challenging experimental datasets demonstrate
31 enhanced map sharpening, robust local validation, and improved structural insights.

32 ***Summary for a broad audience***

33 Cryo-electron microscopy has become a key tool to visualize the structures of proteins and large
34 molecular assemblies. However, cryo-EM maps are not equally reliable everywhere: some regions
35 are well defined, while others are uncertain or ambiguous. Distinguishing between trustworthy and
36 unreliable regions remains challenging, and existing approaches can overlook local problems or
37 unintentionally introduce bias, leading to over-interpretation.

38 Here, we present a new framework that evaluates cryo-EM maps locally, point by point, in an
39 unbiased manner, directly on the reconstructed density. Instead of assigning a single global quality
40 value, our approach produces spatially resolved maps that indicate where the reconstruction is
41 reliable and where it is not. This local, unbiased evaluation allows users to assess map quality,
42 resolution, and directional effects in a consistent manner, and can also be used to enhance maps
43 without artificially creating unsupported features.

44 Importantly, the same local measures can be applied to compare atomic models or post-processed
45 maps against the experimental data. This makes it possible to identify regions that are well

46 supported by the evidence and to flag areas that may require caution or further refinement. Overall,
47 our approach improves the reliability and interpretability of cryo-EM structures and helps
48 researchers build more accurate and trustworthy molecular models.

49 ***Introduction***

50 Cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM) has rapidly emerged as a powerhouse technique in structural
51 biology, enabling routine determination of macromolecular structures at near-atomic or even
52 atomic resolution (Nakane, Kotecha et al. 2020, Yip, Fischer et al. 2020). These breakthroughs,
53 fueled by advances in hardware and algorithms, have transformed cryo-EM into a mainstream
54 method for elucidating macromolecular complexes in near-native conditions (Chua, Mendez et al.
55 2022). Crucially, cryo-EM also empowers the reconstruction of multiple functional states from
56 conformationally heterogeneous particles, offering unique insights into structural dynamics and
57 biological mechanism (Gomez-Blanco, Kaur et al. 2022, Herreros, Mata et al. 2025).

58 Despite the remarkable progress of cryo-EM, the quality of reconstructed maps is rarely
59 homogeneous. Local variations arise from conformational flexibility, compositional heterogeneity
60 or partial occupancy. Moreover, particle interactions with the air–water interface may introduce
61 preferred particle orientations causing local-directional quality variability in the reconstructions.
62 Such issues complicate the reliable interpretation of maps and can propagate into errors during
63 atomic model building. Furthermore, the recent proliferation of deep-learning-based approaches
64 introduces additional challenges for reliable cryo-EM interpretation. Although these methods can
65 substantially improve map interpretability and reconstruction quality, they often lack explicit local
66 confidence estimates, making it difficult to distinguish genuine structural features from potentially
67 unsupported or hallucinated features. This issue is particularly relevant in low-contrast or
68 heterogeneous regions and may increase the risk of over-interpretation, especially for new or

69 inexperienced users. Consequently, there is a growing need for validation frameworks capable of
70 providing robust local reliability measures alongside map enhancement and reconstruction
71 strategies. The cryo-EM community has increasingly recognized the importance of validating
72 obtained cryo-EM maps and atomic models built from them (Lawson et al., 2021), (Kleywegt et
73 al., 2024).

74 Several local approaches have been developed to estimate resolution or detect problematic
75 regions from single cryo-EM maps, including for example ResMap (Kucukelbir, Sigworth et al.
76 2014), MonoRes (Vilas, Gomez-Blanco et al. 2018), LocOccupancy and LocBFactor (Kaur,
77 Gomez-Blanco et al. 2021) and Occupy (Forsberg, Shah et al. 2023). However, these methods
78 present important limitations: they are not based on unbiased strategies as Gold-standard,
79 introduced to avoid overfitting in cryo-EM map refinement (Scheres and Chen 2012), and with the
80 exception of ResMap, rely on signal amplitudes while neglecting phase information. Because
81 phase consistency determines the spatial localization and interpretability of density, amplitude-
82 only measures can overlook local reconstruction artefacts. Furthermore, local resolution methods
83 based on windowed FSC estimations between half maps have also been proposed (Cardone,
84 Heymann et al. 2013). These approaches require user-defined windows, and the estimated local
85 resolution depends on their size, reflecting a trade-off between spatial localization and spectral
86 robustness. More recently, deep learning-based approaches have appeared for the analysis of cryo-
87 EM maps (Ramírez-Aportela, Mota et al. 2019),(Avramov, Vyeniello et al. 2019), (Dai, Dong et
88 al. 2023), (Feng, Chen et al. 2024). These methods can rapidly assess local map quality with
89 minimal user input. However, as data-driven interpolators, these approaches are unreliable outside
90 their training regime, such as for maps affected by anisotropy, flexibility, or reconstruction

91 artefacts (Lander 2024), and their limited interpretability of their decision-making process further
92 limits confidence in novel cases, undermining their use as general-purpose validation tools.

93 Moreover, different methods have been proposed to characterize anisotropy in cryo-EM
94 reconstructions. Tools such as 3DFSC (Tan, Baldwin et al. 2017) and FSO (Vilas and Tagare 2023)
95 quantify directional resolution using Fourier-space measures derived from directional FSC, while
96 cryoEF (Naydenova and Russo 2017) evaluates the uniformity of the particle orientation
97 distribution and its effect on angular information content. These approaches provide map-level
98 assessments of anisotropy. In parallel, directional local resolution methods such as MonoDir
99 (Vilas, Tagare et al. 2020) extend traditional local resolution analysis by decomposing the
100 resolution at each voxel into directional components. However, as recently demonstrated
101 (Sanchez-Garcia, Gaullier et al. 2024), all these directional-based approaches still conflate
102 anisotropy arising from molecular geometry with anisotropy introduced by the reconstruction and
103 the orientation distribution, limiting their ability to disentangle shape-driven effects from true
104 reconstruction anisotropy.

105 Beyond validation, the interpretability of cryo-EM maps also depends critically on post-
106 processing procedures aimed at enhancing map contrast and resolvability. Several local
107 enhancement strategies have been proposed, including approaches such as LocScale (Jakobi et al.,
108 2017) and LocalDeblur (Ramírez-Aportela et al., 2020), which adapt the sharpening locally based
109 on atomic models or local resolution estimates, respectively. Our group introduced LocSpiral
110 (Kaur, Gomez-Blanco et al. 2021), DeepEMhancer (Sanchez-Garcia, Gomez-Blanco et al. 2021)
111 and FrangiFilter (Vargas, Gómez-Pedrero et al. 2022). LocSpiral improves map connectivity based
112 on the spiral phase transform without requiring prior atomic models or local resolution maps,
113 DeepEMhancer corresponds to the first deep learning-based approach to map sharpening and

114 masking and FrangiFilter represents a cryo-EM enhancement approach based on a multiscale
115 tubular filter. More recently, additional and more sophisticated deep learning approaches have
116 been proposed as for example EMReady (He, Li et al. 2023, Cao, Li et al. 2025). The local
117 approaches described above have proved useful for cryo-EM map sharpening and enhancement;
118 however, they do not implement robust cross-validation strategies such as the Gold-standard
119 procedure routinely used in cryo-EM. This limitation is particularly relevant for recent deep-
120 learning-based approaches, which may introduce unsupported or hallucinated features without
121 providing explicit local confidence estimates.

122 Here, we introduce a suite of local, model-free methods designed to enhance high-
123 resolution features and provide unbiased assessments of cryo-EM map quality. In contrast to
124 existing approaches based on single maps or amplitude-only information, our framework operates
125 voxel-wise using independent half-maps following a Gold-standard cross-validation strategy. By
126 jointly analysing local amplitudes and phases through the spiral phase transform, the proposed
127 methods provide improved discrimination between genuine structural signal and reconstruction
128 artefacts, enabling more reliable map enhancement, validation, and interpretation. The suite
129 includes LocSpiral2 for local sharpening, LocFOM and LocQ for quantifying local map
130 agreement, LocSNR for estimating per-voxel signal-to-noise ratios at biologically relevant
131 resolutions, as well as tools for assessing local anisotropy and local resolution. Collectively, these
132 methods require no atomic models, solvent masks, or prior local resolution estimates, reducing
133 overfitting and enabling robust performance in the presence of heterogeneous resolution and
134 variable signal-to-noise across cryo-EM reconstructions.

135 **Results**

136 In this section, we first provide a concise overview of the approaches developed in this work.
137 Detailed technical descriptions are given in the Methods section. We then illustrate their
138 performance through applications to a range of representative cases.

139 **Overview of the proposed approaches**

140 The input to all methods (LocSpiral2, LocFOM, LocSNR, LocQ, LocAnisotropy, and
141 LocResMap) consists of the two unfiltered half-maps ($V_1(\mathbf{r})$, $V_2(\mathbf{r})$) together with a resolution
142 interval $[R_{\min}, R_{\max}]$. Each algorithm first computes the average and difference maps as,

$$143 \quad V(\mathbf{r}) = (V_1(\mathbf{r}) + V_2(\mathbf{r}))/2, \quad D(\mathbf{r}) = (V_1(\mathbf{r}) - V_2(\mathbf{r}))/2 \quad (1)$$

144 These maps and the half maps are band-pass filtered to a given resolution or resolution range
145 $R=1/\omega$. The 3D spiral phase transform is applied to factorize the maps into local amplitude and
146 phase components in the real space as,

$$147 \quad V_{1,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = m_{V_{1,\omega}}(\mathbf{r})\cos(\varphi_{V_{1,\omega}}(\mathbf{r})), \quad V_{2,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = m_{V_{2,\omega}}(\mathbf{r})\cos(\varphi_{V_{2,\omega}}(\mathbf{r}))$$

$$148 \quad V_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = m_{V_{\omega}}(\mathbf{r})\cos(\varphi_{V_{\omega}}(\mathbf{r})), \quad D_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = m_{D_{\omega}}(\mathbf{r})\cos(\varphi_{D_{\omega}}(\mathbf{r})) \quad (2)$$

149 Amplitude maps represent the local signal strength of the maps at resolution $1/\omega$, whereas the
150 cosine of phase terms describe the local shape of the signal bounded to the interval $[-1, 1]$. The
151 proposed methods are based on the analysis and comparisons of these amplitude and phase maps.

152 *LocSpiral2*: This approach performs unbiased local sharpening robust in the presence of
153 heterogeneous resolutions and SNR. For each resolution within the specified resolution range, it

154 computes a binary self-consistency mask comparing the amplitude and phase maps defined in Eq.
155 (2) from half maps, identifying the regions that are reliable in a Gold-standard sense. Only voxels
156 passing this quality test contribute to the final sharpened map at that resolution, which is given by

$$157 \quad \check{V}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\omega} \check{V}_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\omega} Q_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}) \cos(\varphi_{V,\omega}(\mathbf{r})) \quad (3)$$

158 where $Q_{\omega}(\mathbf{r})$ is the binary mask indicating the voxels passing or not passing the quality test at this
159 resolution. In section Methods, we provide detailed information about the quality tests and
160 thresholds used to compute $Q_{\omega}(\mathbf{r})$.

161 *LocFOM*: An approach to determine the local figure of merit between maps. It quantifies the
162 agreement or coherence between the phases of independent half-maps within a given resolution
163 range, as computed by the spiral phase transform. Beyond half-map comparisons, the method can
164 also be applied to evaluate phase consistency between a map and the respective atomic model, or
165 between a map and its sharpened counterpart, thereby providing a versatile metric for local phase
166 reliability.

167 *LocSNR*: This approach estimates per-voxel signal-to-noise ratio to assess signal strength at
168 biologically relevant resolutions, i.e. 4 or 3.5-3, 2.5-2 and $<2 \text{ \AA}$, by comparing the squared
169 amplitude terms of the average and difference maps.

170 *LocQ*: This method computes a local quality metric analogous to $Q_{\omega}(\mathbf{r})$, but instead of producing
171 a binary mask, it assigns a continuous weight or likelihood in the range [0-1]. LocQ jointly
172 evaluates amplitude and phase consistency between independent half-maps, yielding a voxel-wise
173 confidence score based on a Gold-standard approach within the resolution interval $[R_{\min}, R_{\max}]$.

174 *LocAnisotropy*: The method computes the directional amplitude terms of the averaged map along
175 multiple directions using the 3D spiral transform. For each voxel, the standard deviation (σ) and
176 mean (μ) of these directional amplitudes are estimated, and their ratio (σ/μ) is used as a local
177 anisotropy metric. By evaluating this quantity both inside and outside the macromolecular mask,
178 this metric distinguishes anisotropy arising from the molecular shape from anisotropy introduced
179 by the reconstruction process.

180 *LocResMap*: The Gold-standard resolution map is estimated computing at each resolution within
181 the specified resolution range $Q_\omega(\mathbf{r})$, the binary mask indicating the voxels passing or not passing
182 the quality test. For each voxel, the method tracks the highest resolution that passed the quality
183 test. In section Methods, we provide information about the quality tests and thresholds used to
184 compute $Q_\omega(\mathbf{r})$.

185 Figure 1 schematically summarizes the proposed Gold-standard enhancement and validation
186 framework.

187 **LocSpiral2 improves atomic resolvability in high-resolution cryo-EM maps**

188 The power of LocSpiral2 to recover fine structural details is most evident when applied to very
189 high-resolution maps. Accordingly, we analyzed a 1.22 Å single-particle reconstruction of
190 apoferritin (EMD-11638). LocSpiral2 demonstrates superior ability to resolve features that appear
191 merged or incomplete following standard Relion post-processing (deposited emd_11638 map) or
192 EMReady2 enhancement. The density produced by LocSpiral2 (Fig. 2A, solid blue-gray) uncovers
193 distinct structural elements—highlighted by red and black arrows—that remain unresolved in the
194 deposited or EMReady2 maps, which are shown in meshed red and black respectively.

195 Furthermore, LocSpiral2 achieves more comprehensive coverage of the protein structure at
196 equivalent density thresholds compared to both alternative methods (Figure 2B).

197 This qualitative improvement in resolvability is further corroborated by a quantitative
198 analysis of Q-scores (Pintilie et al., 2020) using the corresponding atomic model (PDB:7a4m).
199 Whether assessing the full reconstruction (including waters and ions) or the protein alone,
200 LocSpiral2 consistently outperforms other sharpening techniques across backbones, sidechains,
201 and individual residues (Figures 2C and 2D). As detailed in the distribution profiles and Table 1,
202 LocSpiral2, particularly under the relaxed criterion, yields the highest median and percentile Q-
203 scores. These results support that LocSpiral2 does not merely sharpen the map but also improves
204 the quality and interpretability of high-resolution features.

205 **LocSpiral2 delivers consistent, high-fidelity sharpening across diverse resolutions**

206 The robustness of LocSpiral2 as a general-purpose sharpening tool is demonstrated by its
207 performance across a broad spectrum of structural data, from high-resolution (2.0–2.6 Å) to
208 moderate-resolution (3.0–4.3 Å) reconstructions. In a benchmark comparison involving 29 maps
209 and different post-processing tools, including by cryoTEN (Selvaraj, Wang et al. 2025),
210 DeepEMhancer (Sanchez-Garcia, Gomez-Blanco et al. 2021), EMReady (He, Li et al. 2023),
211 EMReady2 (Cao, Li et al. 2025) and LocScale (Jakobi, Wilmanns et al. 2017), LocSpiral2
212 consistently yielded superior or highly competitive quality metrics (Figure 3). Quantitative
213 evaluations using average Q-scores, EMRinger values, and map-to-model FSC at a 0.5 threshold
214 confirm that LocSpiral2 provides the most significant improvements in the high-resolution regime
215 while remaining on par with the best-performing deep learning methods, EMReady and
216 EMReady2 at moderate resolutions (Tables S1–S3). LocSpiral2 relies on a gold-standard

217 framework using independent half-maps, providing built-in robustness and reliability by
218 minimizing the risk of overfitting and suppressing the propagation of noise-driven or hallucinated
219 features.

220 **LocQ provides intuitive diagnostics of local structural integrity**

221 To evaluate local map quality by jointly analysing amplitude and phase consistency beyond global
222 resolution estimates, we applied our multi-metric validation suite across different resolution ranges
223 to the maps of the PC2 TRP channel (EMD-10418) (Wang, Corey et al. 2020) and human
224 hemoglobin (EMD-31915) (Wang, Corey et al. 2020) reconstructed at reported resolutions of 2.96
225 Å and 3.6 Å respectively (Fig. 4). By integrating LocFOM, LocSNR, and C into the
226 comprehensive LocQ score, we established an intuitive [0-1] quality scale that quantifies the
227 likelihood-like quality of specific density regions. Within this framework, LocQ and LocQ* refer
228 to the relaxed and exigent criteria respectively. This integrated metric reveals that map reliability
229 is rarely uniform. Flexible peripheral regions of both the hemoglobin and TRP channel
230 reconstructions consistently exhibit lower quality scores than the more ordered core regions
231 (Figures 4A and C). In addition, LocQ values progressively decrease when considering higher
232 resolutions, reflecting the reduced reproducibility of high-frequency information between
233 independent half-maps. Furthermore, the individual components of LocQ provide insight into the
234 origin of local quality losses. While LocQ summarizes the overall reliability of a density region,
235 LocFOM and LocSNR allow us to distinguish whether low-quality scores arise from reduced phase
236 consistency between independent half-maps or from reduced local signal-to-noise ratio. In
237 particular, LocFOM highlights regions where phase agreement deteriorates, exposing structural
238 inconsistencies that may remain hidden in the averaged reconstruction (Figures 4B and D).
239 Conversely, LocSNR identifies regions where the signal becomes indistinguishable from the

240 background noise. Together, these complementary metrics provide a mechanistic interpretation of
241 map local quality and facilitate the identification of regions that may require caution during
242 biological interpretation and atomic model building.

243 **LocFOM facilitates validation of map-model agreement and deep learning sharpening**

244 The LocFOM metric provides a robust framework for assessing structural consistency, whether
245 validating an atomic model or evaluating the fidelity of deep learning-enhanced reconstructions.
246 We first demonstrated this by comparing the primary experimental maps for the polycystin-2
247 (PC2) TRP channel (EMD-10418) and human hemoglobin (EMD-31915) against maps simulated
248 from their respective atomic models (PDB IDs: 7vde and 6t9n). In both cases, LocFOM was
249 computed over a resolution range of 2.5–4 Å against simulated maps generated at 2 Å resolution.

250 The TRP channel analysis reveals high phase consistency across most of the reconstruction,
251 yet the metric successfully pinpoints localized discrepancies where the primary map and the atomic
252 model diverge (Figures 5A and B). Similarly, for the hemoglobin reconstruction, LocFOM values
253 highlight specific regions of model-to-map divergence that are not immediately obvious from the
254 density alone, providing a quantitative measure of phase agreement (Figures 5C–D).

255 Beyond traditional model validation, LocFOM serves as a tool for quantifying the
256 structural similarity between deposited maps and those post-processed by deep learning tools like
257 DeepEMhancer (Sanchez-Garcia, Gomez-Blanco et al. 2021) and EMReady2 (Cao, Li et al. 2025).
258 For the TRP channel, the metric effectively maps the level of phase agreement between the primary
259 density and its enhanced counterparts; these LocFOM values reveal exactly where the sharpening
260 process preserves or alters the original phase information (Figures 5E–F). By reversing this
261 analysis and mapping LocFOM onto the post-processed reconstructions, the tool identifies regions

262 of potential over-sharpening or artifactual density that deviate from the experimental evidence
263 (Figures 5G–H). This diagnostic capability is further confirmed by the hemoglobin analysis, which
264 exposes local inconsistencies introduced during post-processing, suggesting that modelling
265 process should be done based on the original experimental data in those regions (Figures 5I–L).

266 **LocAnisotropy provides a shape-independent metric for directional artifacts**

267 By design, the LocAnisotropy metric distinguishes between anisotropy arising from the molecular
268 shape and reconstruction-induced anisotropies by comparing values inside and outside the solvent
269 mask. While anisotropy scores calculated inside the mask reflect the physical geometry of the
270 macromolecule, values measured in the solvent region relate to reconstruction-induced
271 anisotropies (Sanchez-Garcia, Gaullier et al. 2024). This distinction is grounded in the statistical
272 behavior of noise: in an ideal, isotropic reconstruction, Fourier amplitudes in noise-dominated
273 regions follow a Rayleigh distribution with a theoretical coefficient of variation of approximately
274 0.52 (see Methods). Consequently, isotropic regions exhibit baseline values near this limit,
275 whereas reconstruction-induced anisotropy increases directional dispersion, driving these values
276 significantly higher. In practice, slight deviations from this value are expected due to finite angular
277 sampling, spatial correlations, and the presence of coloured noise in cryo-EM data.

278 We show this principle across diverse datasets, demonstrating that the metric remains
279 unaffected by the specific shape of the macromolecule. Figure 6 illustrates this behaviour by
280 showing per-voxel LocAnisotropy maps for isotropic and anisotropic reconstructions at both high-
281 and low-density thresholds. High-quality, nearly isotropic reconstructions such as apoferritin
282 (EMD-11638) and beta-galactosidase (EMD-2984) yielded stable solvent-averaged values
283 between 0.42 and 0.49, despite their different morphologies. In contrast, datasets known for
284 preferred orientations and anisotropy, such as the influenza hemagglutinin trimer (EMD-38084)

285 and PSI-8LHCI (EMD-38086), showed markedly elevated solvent averages of 0.60 and 0.79,
286 respectively (Figure 6). These results indicate that solvent-averaged LocAnisotropy values below
287 0.5 are characteristic of well-behaved reconstructions, whereas values exceeding 0.6 are associated
288 with significant reconstruction-induced anisotropy, regardless of the macromolecule's complexity.

289 **LocResMap provides robust Gold-standard estimation of map local resolution**

290 To evaluate LocResMap as a Gold-standard local resolution estimator, we applied the method to
291 the polycystin-2 (PC2) TRP channel (EMD-10418) and human hemoglobin (EMD-31915), whose
292 reported global resolutions are 2.96 Å and 3.6 Å, respectively. Local resolution maps obtained
293 using the relaxed and exigent criteria are shown in Figure S1 and compared with corresponding
294 MonoRes estimates computed at different significance thresholds. For both datasets, LocResMap
295 yielded average local resolution values consistent with the reported global resolutions, particularly
296 when using the relaxed criterion, which is conceptually related to the 0.143 FSC threshold. These
297 results indicate that LocResMap provides robust and physically interpretable local resolution
298 estimates while maintaining the Gold-standard validation framework introduced in this work.

299 **Application of Gold-standard local validation in protein-ligand complexes**

300 We evaluated the quality of the cryo-EM structure for a Bicycle molecule in complex with the
301 SARS-CoV-1 Spike protein (EMD-51660; PDB code 9GXG), which was reconstructed to a
302 reported resolution of 1.92 Å (Harman, Gaynor et al. 2025). The analysis yielded several key
303 metrics that collectively affirm the structure's high quality.

304 Figure 7A shows that LocQ scores were consistently near 1, indicating good local quality,
305 while the LocSNR values were predominantly above our threshold ($q_{SNR} = 1$), signifying high
306 confidence in the map. The LocFOM metric, which assesses the phase consistency between the

307 experimental map and a map generated from the atomic model, was satisfactory. Finally,
308 the LocAnisotropy calculations certified the high degree of isotropy of the reconstruction as can
309 be seen in Fig. 7B. The average values of LocAnisotropy within and outside the solvent mask
310 correspond to 0.37/0.38 confirming the absence of issues related to preferred particle orientations.
311 Fig. 7C, shows LocSpiral2 map of the complex locating the position of the E2 and E4 Bicycle
312 molecules binders. Finally, Figures 7 (D–G) present magnified views of the E4 binder, including
313 the LocSNR-colored map (D), LocFOM-colored map (E), primary map with corresponding PDB
314 fitted (F) and LocSpiral2 map to evaluate the local sharpening (G). Taken together, these results
315 demonstrate that such validation tools are invaluable for assessing protein-ligand cryo-EM
316 structures. They specifically increase confidence in the accuracy of modelled ligand poses, a
317 critical aspect of structure-based drug discovery. In this field, resolving subtle structural features
318 is critical, as even seemingly minor interactions can significantly impact the affinities and
319 properties of a protein-ligand system. The LocSpiral2 map at the E4 epitope (Figure 7G)
320 demonstrates this by revealing additional density for a potential salt bridge between Lys182 and
321 Glu180, while also resolving the side chains of Leu176 and the Bicycle molecule Isoleucine-1.

322 ***Discussion***

323 In this work, we introduce a unified Gold-standard framework for the local validation,
324 enhancement, and interpretation of cryo-EM reconstructions. By operating voxel-wise in real
325 space and explicitly combining amplitude and phase information from independent half-maps, our
326 approach addresses several long-standing limitations of existing local validation and post-
327 processing strategies. Rather than providing a collection of isolated metrics, the framework

328 integrates complementary descriptors of map quality, resolution, and anisotropy into a coherent
329 methodology grounded in cross-validation principles.

330 A central conceptual advance of this work is the explicit use of local phase information for
331 map assessment. Most current cryo-EM local validation metrics rely primarily on signal
332 amplitudes, implicitly assuming that phase information is reliable. However, phase consistency is
333 a fundamental determinant of map interpretability. By exploiting the spiral phase transform, we
334 extract localized phase estimates in real space and directly quantify their agreement between
335 independent half-maps. This enables voxel-wise measures such as the local figure of merit
336 (LocFOM), which provides a physically meaningful assessment of phase reliability that
337 complements amplitude-based metrics. Importantly, LocFOM can also be applied to assess the
338 phase consistency between experimental maps and density maps derived from atomic models or
339 alternative post-processed maps, facilitating the detection of locally inconsistent or potentially
340 mis-traced regions. This dual applicability highlights the potential of this metric to bridge map
341 validation and model assessment.

342 The adoption of a Gold-standard strategy at the voxel level represents another key
343 contribution. While Gold-standard procedures are routinely used for global resolution estimation
344 and refinement, most local sharpening and validation approaches still operate on single maps,
345 increasing the risk of overfitting and noise amplification. The methods introduced here are
346 computed from independent half-maps, ensuring that local measurements reflect genuine signal
347 reproducibility rather than post-processing artefacts. This property is particularly relevant in the
348 context of aggressive sharpening or learning-based enhancement, where the absence of intrinsic
349 validation can obscure the presence of non-supported features.

350 Our results demonstrate that LocSpiral2 provides robust local sharpening across a broad
351 range of resolutions, improving map interpretability and atomic detail while preventing overfitting
352 and potential structural hallucination. In contrast to global B-factor sharpening or data-driven
353 approaches, LocSpiral2 selectively enhances signal only where it is supported by Gold-standard
354 consistency. Benchmarking against state-of-the-art post-processing methods shows that
355 LocSpiral2 yields good performance in terms of Q-score, EMRinger, and map–model FSC,
356 particularly for high-resolution reconstructions.

357 Beyond sharpening, the proposed metrics enable a fine-grained interpretation of local map
358 reliability. LocQ provides an intuitive quality score that integrates phase agreement, signal-to-
359 noise ratio, and amplitude consistency, allowing the identification of regions with varying
360 confidence levels. The characterization of anisotropy constitutes another important aspect of this
361 work. Existing approaches to assess anisotropy, such as 3DFSC, cryoEF, FSO, or directional local
362 resolution methods, either provide global descriptors or directional decompositions that remain
363 inherently confounded by the molecular shape. By defining anisotropy as the relative dispersion
364 of directional amplitudes and explicitly evaluating this quantity in solvent regions, LocAnisotropy
365 isolates reconstruction-induced anisotropy from shape-driven effects. The empirical separation
366 observed between well-behaved reference datasets and reconstructions affected by preferred
367 orientation is consistent with the theoretical baseline derived for isotropic noise-dominated
368 regions, in which LocAnisotropy approaches the coefficient of variation of a Rayleigh-distributed
369 amplitude field (~ 0.5). Deviations above this baseline therefore reflect additional directional
370 variability arising from reconstruction-induced anisotropy, further supporting the robustness of
371 this formulation. Similarly, LocResMap extends local resolution estimation by embedding it
372 within the same Gold-standard framework. Rather than relying solely on local amplitude statistics,

373 LocResMap determines, for each voxel, the highest resolution at which phase consistency, signal-
374 to-noise ratio, and modulation contrast remain satisfied. This yields conservative and physically
375 interpretable local resolution estimates that agree well with reported global resolutions.

376 Several limitations should nevertheless be acknowledged. The proposed framework relies
377 on the availability of properly processed Gold-standard half-maps properly aligned. In addition,
378 although the spiral transform is computationally efficient, the evaluation across multiple
379 resolutions and directions can still be demanding for very large volumes. Future work will focus
380 on further optimization, GPU acceleration, and tighter integration with established cryo-EM
381 processing pipelines.

382 In summary, this work establishes a general Gold-standard framework for local cryo-EM
383 map validation and enhancement, unifying sharpening, quality assessment, anisotropy analysis,
384 resolution estimation, and map–model consistency within a single methodology. By explicitly
385 incorporating local phase information and enforcing voxel-wise cross-validation, the proposed
386 approach improves the reliability and interpretability of cryo-EM reconstructions and provides a
387 principled foundation for downstream structural analysis and atomic modelling.

388 ***Acknowledgments***

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391 ***Methods***

392 All methods introduced in this work build upon the 3D spiral phase transform (Kaur, Gomez-
393 Blanco et al. 2021), which for band-limited maps factorizes the signal in real space into an

394 amplitude (or modulation) term that reflects its local signal strength, and a phase component that
 395 encodes its spatial structure. In the following, we detail how this transform is applied to different
 396 tasks: map sharpening (LocSpiral2) and local quality estimation (LocFOM, LocSNR, LocQ,
 397 LocAnisotropy, and LocResMap). In all cases, the methods are formulated within a Gold-standard
 398 framework using independent half-maps.

399 **3D spiral phase transform**

400 The spiral phase transform is a Fourier operator that can factorize a 3D map band-pass filtered at
 401 a given resolution or frequency ω into its amplitude and phase terms in real space. Without loss of
 402 generality a 3D map band-pass filtered at frequency ω can be modelled as a 3D phase modulated
 403 signal given by

$$404 \quad V(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\omega} V_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\omega} \left(b_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}) + m_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}) \cos(\varphi_{\omega}(\mathbf{r})) \right) \quad (4)$$

405 where V is the cryo-EM map, V_{ω} is a band-passed map filtered at frequency ω , b_{ω} the 3D
 406 background or DC term, m_{ω} the 3D amplitude map, φ_{ω} the 3D modulating phase and $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)$.
 407 Since in practice, we are interested in spatial frequencies higher than 1/10-1/20 1/Å and the
 408 background is predominantly confined to low frequencies, we can assume that the DC term is
 409 constant within our interesting frequency range, and the map can be approximated by its high-pass
 410 filtered version for frequencies within our defined range

$$411 \quad V(\mathbf{r}) \sim V_{HP}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\omega} m_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}) \cos(\varphi_{\omega}(\mathbf{r})) \quad (5)$$

412 The 3D spiral (Hilbert) transform applied to our band-passed map $V_{HP}(\mathbf{r})$ produces its quadrature
 413 signal, though only up to an undetermined sign that is given by

$$414 \quad \mathbf{H}\{V_{HP}(\mathbf{r})\} = - \sum_{\omega} s_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}) m_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}) \sin(\varphi_{\omega}(\mathbf{r})) \quad (6)$$

415 where $s_{\omega}(\mathbf{r})$ is a function with range +1 or -1 showing the sign ambiguity and is given by (Antonio
 416 Quiroga and Servin 2003, Servin, Quiroga et al. 2003, Kaur, Gomez-Blanco et al. 2021)

417
$$s_\omega(\mathbf{r}) = \nabla V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \nabla \varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r}) \quad (7)$$

418 The sign ambiguity arises because the gradients of the phase $\nabla \varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r})$, and of the map
 419 $\nabla V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})$ can be either parallel or antiparallel, and we do not have direct access to the local phase.
 420 This ambiguity reflects the cosine term in Eq. (5) and the fact that m_ω , varies slowly compared
 421 to φ_ω as shown in (Antonio Quiroga and Servin 2003, Servin, Quiroga et al. 2003, Kaur, Gomez-
 422 Blanco et al. 2021). The 3D spiral transform $\mathbf{H}\{\cdot\}$ is given by the following operator,

423
$$\mathbf{H}\{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})\} = FT^{-1} \left\{ \frac{-i\mathbf{q}}{|\mathbf{q}|} FT\{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})\} \right\} \quad (8)$$

424 with \mathbf{q} the 3D Fourier coordinates. From Eq. (4) and (5), we can obtain an estimation of $\varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r})$
 425 affected by an indetermination in its sign by

426
$$\varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r}) \cong \arctan \left[\frac{Q\{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})\}}{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})} \right] = -s_\omega(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \arctan \left[\frac{FT^{-1} \left\{ \frac{-i\mathbf{q}}{|\mathbf{q}|} FT\{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})\} \right\}}{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})} \right] \quad (9)$$

427 and the amplitude, cosine and sine terms separately as

428
$$m_\omega(\mathbf{r}) = \left(\left(V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) \right)^2 + \left(Q\{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})\} \right)^2 \right)^{1/2}$$

429
$$\cos(\varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r})) \cong \cos \left(\arctan \left[\frac{Q\{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})\}}{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})} \right] \right) = \cos \left(\arctan \left[\frac{FT^{-1} \left\{ \frac{-i\mathbf{q}}{|\mathbf{q}|} FT\{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})\} \right\}}{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})} \right] \right)$$

430
$$\sin(\varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r})) \cong \sin \left(\arctan \left[\frac{Q\{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})\}}{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})} \right] \right) = -s_\omega(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \sin \left(\arctan \left[\frac{FT^{-1} \left\{ \frac{-i\mathbf{q}}{|\mathbf{q}|} FT\{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})\} \right\}}{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})} \right] \right) \quad (10)$$

431 Using these expressions, $\cos(\varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r}))$ and $m_\omega(\mathbf{r})$ are uniquely determined for each frequency ω ,
 432 whereas the term $\sin(\varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r}))$ is obtained only up to a sign.

433 **Justification of the quality thresholds**

434 The quality criteria used in this work are based on the comparison of two independent half-maps
 435 in terms of their 3D phases and amplitudes, as obtained from the spiral phase transform. These
 436 criteria are directly linked to standards well established in both cryo-EM and X-ray crystallography
 437 validation. In crystallography, the interpretability of electron density depends critically on phase
 438 accuracy: phase errors below $\sim 40^\circ$ are generally required for confident model building, while
 439 errors up to $\sim 60^\circ$ may still allow tracing of molecular boundaries, albeit with limited detail
 440 (Rosenthal and Henderson 2003). This criterion is formalized by the figure of merit (FOM),
 441 defined as the expected value of the cosine of the phase error, $\langle \cos(\varphi) \rangle$, which directly links phase
 442 accuracy to map quality.

443 In cryo-EM, the equivalent concept is captured by the Fourier shell correlation (FSC)
 444 between two half-maps, which can be related to the FOM by $C_{\text{ref}} = \sqrt{2\text{FSC}/(1 + \text{FSC})}$ (Rosenthal
 445 and Henderson 2003). Within this framework, an FSC threshold of 0.143 corresponds to a FOM
 446 of 0.5 (average phase error $\approx 60^\circ$), while an FSC of 0.5 corresponds to a FOM of 0.81 ($\approx 35^\circ$).

447 In this work, we compute localized phase error metrics directly in real space using the
 448 spiral phase transform. The localized FOM (LocFOM) is defined as

$$449 \quad \text{LocFOM}_\omega(\mathbf{r}) = \cos(\Delta\varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r})) = \cos(\varphi_{1,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) - \varphi_{2,\omega}(\mathbf{r})) \quad (11)$$

450 where $\varphi_{1,\omega}$ and $\varphi_{2,\omega}$ are the local phase maps computed from the two half-maps. Note that the
 451 cosine term in Eq. (11) eliminates the sign ambiguity of Eq. (9) since it is an even function.
 452 Similarly, the local SNR can be estimated from the amplitude maps of the average and difference
 453 volumes as

$$454 \quad \text{LocSNR}_\omega(\mathbf{r}) = \left(\frac{m_{V,\omega}(\mathbf{r})}{m_{D,\omega}(\mathbf{r})} \right)^2 - 1 \quad (12)$$

455 with $m_{V,\omega}(\mathbf{r})$ and $m_{D,\omega}(\mathbf{r})$ the amplitude terms of the average and difference maps, respectively
 456 (Please see Supplementary Material, section Local signal to noise ratio). The local SNR is thus
 457 calculated from the average map combining both half maps. Accordingly, an SNR threshold of 1
 458 was adopted, indicating the same signal and noise power. Finally, we impose an additional
 459 consistency requirement on the relative amplitude of the two half-maps, expressed as a local
 460 contrast metric given by

$$461 \quad C_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{|m_{V_1,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) - m_{V_2,\omega}(\mathbf{r})|}{m_{V_1,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) + m_{V_2,\omega}(\mathbf{r})} \quad (13)$$

462 which is constrained to remain below 0.3.

463 As a summary of this section, we adopt two alternative quality thresholds for the localized
 464 figure-of-merit: a rigorous or exigent criterion (FOM = 0.81, phase error $\approx 35^\circ$) corresponding to
 465 $q_{FOM} = 0.81$, or a more relaxed criterion (FOM = 0.5, phase error $\approx 60^\circ$) corresponding to $q_{FOM} =$
 466 0.5. In both cases we use the same SNR and contrast requirements: $q_{SNR} = 1$ and contrast $q_C =$
 467 0.3.

468 **Local enhanced map (LocSpiral2)**

469 We propose here a robust local map enhancement method based on the Gold-standard approach
 470 and the spiral transform, which only requires as input corresponding half maps and a resolution
 471 range. The proposed approach performs band-pass filtering of average, difference and half maps,
 472 within the input resolution range. Each band-pass filtered map is factorized into its amplitude and
 473 phase terms by the spiral phase transform. These terms are used to create a quality binary mask
 474 based on the quality criteria outlined above as

$$475 \quad Q_{FOM,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = \cos(\varphi_{1,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) - \varphi_{2,\omega}(\mathbf{r})) > q_{FOM}$$

$$476 \quad Q_{SNR,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = \left(\frac{m_{V,\omega}(\mathbf{r})}{m_{D,\omega}(\mathbf{r})}\right)^2 - 1 > q_{SNR}$$

477
$$Q_{C,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{|m_{V_1,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) - m_{V_2,\omega}(\mathbf{r})|}{m_{V_1,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) + m_{V_2,\omega}(\mathbf{r})} < q_C$$

478
$$Q_\omega(\mathbf{r}) = Q_{FOM,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot Q_{SNR,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot Q_{C,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (14)$$

479 This quality mask is used to normalize map amplitudes in real space across frequencies and to
 480 suppress signals below our quality threshold, as these likely correspond to noise at that frequency.

481 After this nonlinear amplitude transformation, the enhanced map at a given frequency ω is given
 482 by

483
$$\check{V}_\omega(\mathbf{r}) = Q_\omega(\mathbf{r}) \cos(\varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r})) \quad (15)$$

484 and the final enhanced map

485
$$\check{V}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_\omega \check{V}_\omega(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_\omega Q_\omega(\mathbf{r}) \cos(\varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r})) \quad (16)$$

486 In case a solvent mask is provided, the approach can compute another binary quality mask
 487 following the approach used by our previous LocSpiral method. In this case, we obtain the 90-
 488 95% quantile of the empirical noise amplitude probability distribution at frequency ω by selecting
 489 amplitude values of the average map not included in the solvent mask ($m_{V,\omega}^N(q=95\%)$). Then, we
 490 can define an additional quality mask as

491
$$Q_{N,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = (m_{V,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) > m_{V,\omega}^N(q=95\%)) \quad (17)$$

492 In this case, Eq. (16) is rewritten as

493
$$\check{V}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_\omega \check{V}_\omega(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_\omega Q_{N,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) Q_\omega(\mathbf{r}) \cos(\varphi_\omega(\mathbf{r})) \quad (18)$$

494 **Local figure of merit determination (LocFOM)**

495 This approach applies the 3D spiral phase transform to compute phase maps ($\varphi_{1,\omega}$, $\varphi_{2,\omega}$) from
 496 band-passed half maps within the input resolution range. The local phase agreement is then
 497 quantified through the cosine of the phase difference as shown in Eq. (11), which provides a voxel-

498 wise analogue of the crystallographic figure of merit. Values close to 1 indicate high local phase
499 consistency (small phase error), while values approaching 0 reflect random or inconsistent phases.

500 **Local signal-to-noise ratio determination (LocSNR)**

501 The spiral phase transform is applied to the band-passed average and difference maps obtaining
502 their respective amplitude maps $m_{V,\omega}(\mathbf{r})$ and $m_{D,\omega}(\mathbf{r})$. These maps are used to estimate locally
503 the SNR as shown in Eq. (12).

504 **Local map quality determination (LocQ)**

505 As before, band-pass filtered average, difference and half maps within the input resolution range
506 are processed with the spiral phase transform to compute the three basic quality descriptors: the
507 local figure of merit $\text{LocFOM}_\omega(\mathbf{r})$, the local signal-to-noise ratio $\text{LocSNR}_\omega(\mathbf{r})$ and the local
508 amplitude contrast $C_\omega(\mathbf{r})$ as shown in Eq. (11-13). These quantities are then combined into a single
509 local quality score,

$$510 \text{LocQ}_\omega(\mathbf{r}) = \exp(-\text{LocFOM}_\omega^2(\mathbf{r})/q_{FOM}^2)(1 - \exp(-\text{LocSNR}_\omega^2(\mathbf{r})/q_{SNR}^2))\exp(-C_\omega^2(\mathbf{r})/q_C^2)$$

511 (19)

512 By construction, LocQ is the product of likelihood-like transformations of the underlying metrics,
513 each bounded in the range [0, 1]. This definition provides an intuitive and easy-to-interpret local
514 map quality estimator: values close to 1 indicate regions of high phase agreement, strong signal-
515 to-noise ratio, and consistent half-map amplitudes, while lower values highlight areas where the
516 density is less reliable.

517 **Local anisotropy determination (LocAnisotropy)**

518 To quantify directional anisotropy, the average map is band-pass filtered within the input
 519 resolution range. A directionally oriented Gaussian kernel in Fourier space is then used to define
 520 the directional 3D spiral transform along direction \mathbf{d} as,

$$521 \quad \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{d}}\{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})\} = \text{FT}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{-i\mathbf{q}}{|\mathbf{q}|} D_{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{q}) \cdot \text{FT}\{V_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r})\} \right\} \quad (20)$$

522 where $D_{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{q})$ denotes the directional Gaussian kernel oriented along direction \mathbf{d} given by

$$523 \quad D_{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{q}) = \exp\left(-(\hat{\mathbf{q}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{d}})^2 / \sigma_{\mathbf{d}}^2\right) \quad (21)$$

524 with $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{d}}$ being normalized vectors, ' \cdot ', the inner product operator and $\sigma_{\mathbf{d}}$ controlling angular
 525 selectivity with a typical value of 5° . The directional 3D spiral transform is used to determine the
 526 directional amplitude of the average map along direction \mathbf{d} , $(m_{V,\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r}))$, representing the local
 527 signal strength along direction \mathbf{d} within the resolution range.

528 Directional amplitude maps are computed for ~ 100 – 200 orientations uniformly covering
 529 the sphere, using Fibonacci sphere sampling. This deterministic strategy distributes points nearly
 530 uniformly across the sphere by combining equidistant latitudes with golden-angle rotations
 531 ($\sim 137.5^\circ$), thereby avoiding pole clustering and ensuring efficient angular coverage (González
 532 2009). The approach obtains the standard deviation and the average of $m_{V,\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r})$ across the
 533 orientations. Finally, the local anisotropy map is computed as a relative magnitude by comparing
 534 the dispersion of the local signal strength with respect to its expected value or average as

$$535 \quad \text{LocAnisotropy}(\mathbf{r}) = \sigma\{m_{V,\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r})\} / E\{m_{V,\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r})\} \quad (22)$$

536 where $\sigma\{\cdot\}$ and $E\{\cdot\}$ denote the standard deviation and average operators, respectively. Unlike
 537 global anisotropy measures, LocAnisotropy enables assessment of directional resolution
 538 heterogeneity within specific regions of the map. This includes analysis both inside and outside
 539 solvent masks, thereby distinguishing anisotropy arising from the macromolecular shape from that

540 introduced by preferred orientations or reconstruction artifacts (Sanchez-Garcia, Gaullier et al.
 541 2024).

542 **Theoretical baseline of LocAnisotropy in isotropic noise-dominated regions**

543 To interpret the values of LocAnisotropy in solvent regions, it is useful to consider the ideal case
 544 of an isotropic, noise-dominated map. In the absence of directional bias, the directional amplitudes
 545 $m_{V,\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r})$ obtained from the directional spiral transform can be approximated as the modulus of a
 546 circular complex Gaussian variable, corresponding to the complex analytical signal $V_{HP,\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r}) =$
 547 $m_{V,\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r})\exp(i\varphi_{\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r}))$. In the ideal case where the underlying fluctuations can be approximated as
 548 white Gaussian noise, the directional amplitudes follow a Rayleigh distribution, where χ is the
 549 scale parameter (Goodman 1985). For a Rayleigh-distributed variable, the mean and standard
 550 deviation are given by

$$551 \quad \mathbb{E}\{m_{V,\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r})\} = \chi\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}; \quad \sigma\{m_{V,\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r})\} = \chi\sqrt{\frac{4-\pi}{2}} \quad (23)$$

552 Therefore, the expected coefficient of variation, which is precisely the quantity used in
 553 LocAnisotropy, is

$$554 \quad \text{LocAnisotropy}(\mathbf{r}) = \sigma\{m_{V,\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r})\}/\mathbb{E}\{m_{V,\omega}^{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{r})\} = \sqrt{\frac{4-\pi}{\pi}} \approx 0.52 \quad (24)$$

555 This value provides a theoretical baseline for isotropic, noise-dominated regions. In practice, cryo-
 556 EM reconstructions do not satisfy the assumptions of white independent noise exactly, and slight
 557 deviations from this limit are expected due to finite angular sampling, coloured noise, and
 558 correlations introduced by band-limiting and reconstruction procedures. Nevertheless, values close
 559 to this baseline are consistent with well-behaved isotropic reconstructions, whereas systematically
 560 higher values indicate additional directional variability caused by reconstruction-induced
 561 anisotropy.

562 **Local resolution map (LocResMap)**

563 The local resolution map using the Gold-standard approach is derived from the voxel-wise quality
564 mask $Q_\omega(\mathbf{r})$. For each spatial position \mathbf{r} , the method identifies the highest spatial frequency ω (i.e.
565 the finest resolution $1/\omega$) within the input resolution range at which our local quality criterion—
566 combining the figure of merit (FOM), the local signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), and the amplitude
567 contrast between half-maps—remains satisfied. Formally, the local resolution is defined as

568
$$\text{LocResMap}(\mathbf{r}) = \max_{\omega \in [\omega_{\min}, \omega_{\max}]} \{1/\omega \mid Q_\omega(\mathbf{r}) = 1\} \quad (25)$$

569 where $Q_\omega(\mathbf{r})$ is a binary indicator that takes the value 1 if the quality test is fulfilled at frequency
570 ω and 0 otherwise. In this way, LocResMap provides a spatially resolved estimate of the highest
571 reliable resolution supported by the data, linked to Gold-standard half-map consistency and local
572 signal quality.

573 ***Data availability***

574 The data supporting the findings of this study are openly available from the Electron Microscopy
575 Data Bank (EMDB) and the Protein Data Bank (PDB). The EMDB accession codes used in this
576 work are: EMD-0004, EMD-0282, EMD-0311, EMD-0520, EMD-0560, EMD-2984, EMD-
577 10337, EMD-10350, EMD-10365, EMD-10418, EMD-10492, EMD-10649, EMD-10817, EMD-
578 11112, EMD-11557, EMD-11624, EMD-11638, EMD-10574, EMD-14429, EMD-14522, EMD-
579 14528, EMD-16433, EMD-17298, EMD-17583, EMD-23786, EMD-26957, EMD-28147, EMD-
580 31911, EMD-31915, EMD-34368, EMD-35453, EMD-36468, EMD-38084, EMD-38086, EMD-

581 39867 and EMD-51660. The corresponding PDB accession codes used for model-based analyses
582 are: 7A4M, 7VDE, 6T9N and 9GXG.

583 ***Code availability***

584 The software supporting the findings of this study is openly available at GitHub:
585 <https://github.com/laviervargas/scipion-em-spiral>.

586 ***Author contributions***

587 J.V. conceived and led the study. J.V., J.B.C., and J.G.P. designed the theoretical framework and
588 developed the algorithms. J.V. implemented the core computational methods and supervised the
589 methodological development. J.V., A.V.F., S.P., G.A.B., and K.H.B. performed data analysis and
590 validation experiments. J.V. and K.H.B. wrote the manuscript. J.V. coordinated the project. All
591 authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

592 ***Competing interests***

593 The authors declare the following competing financial interest(s): S.P. and G.A.B. are shareholders
594 and/or share option holders in Bicycle Therapeutics plc, the parent company of Bicycle Tx Ltd.

595 **Figure Captions**

596 **Figure 1 Overview of the proposed Gold-standard enhancement and validation methods for**

597 **cryo-EM. (A)** Schematic representation of the local spiral phase decomposition applied to a cryo-

598 EM map V . The 3D spiral phase transform factorizes the map locally and voxel-wise into

599 amplitude and phase terms, yielding a local analytic signal $\hat{V}_{HP,\omega}(\mathbf{r}) = m_{\omega}(\mathbf{r})\exp(is_{\omega}(\mathbf{r})\varphi_{\omega}(\mathbf{r}))$.

600 The amplitude term $m_{\omega}(\mathbf{r})$ is primarily related to local signal strength and signal-to-noise ratio,

601 whereas the phase term $\varphi_{\omega}(\mathbf{r})$ encodes local structural information. **(B)** General workflow of the

602 proposed Gold-standard framework. Independent half-maps (V_1 and V_2) are combined into average

603 (V) and difference (D) maps and analysed within a selected frequency range $[\omega_{min}, \omega_{max}]$ using

604 the spiral phase transform. Local amplitudes and phases obtained from the factorization are

605 subsequently used for local sharpening (LocSpiral2), voxel-wise validation metrics (LocFOM,

606 LocSNR, LocQ and LocResMap), and directional anisotropy estimation (LocAnisotropy).

607 **Figure 2 Gold-standard framework for local enhancement of cryo-EM maps. (A)** Sharpened

608 density maps of apoferritin (EMD-11638) obtained using LocSpiral2 and the relaxed criterion,

609 $q_{FOM} = 0.5$, (solid surface in blue-gray), Relion/deposited emd_11638 map (red mesh) and

610 EMReady2 (black mesh). **(B)** Superposition of LocSpiral2 (blue-gray), EMReady2 (yellow), and

611 Relion/deposited (red) reconstructions displayed at comparable contour levels, highlighting

612 differences in protein coverage and map continuity. **(C)** Violin plots of Q-scores computed for

613 backbone, side chains, and residues from the deposited map, LocSpiral2 (relaxed criterion),

614 LocSpiral2* (exigent criterion), and EMReady2 maps. Q-scores are reported both for the complete

615 map, including waters and ions, and for the protein region only. In these figures, solid and dashed

616 lines indicate the median and the 25th (Q1) and 75th (Q3) percentiles, respectively.

617 **Figure 3 Benchmarking LocSpiral2 for robust local map sharpening.** Boxplots summarizing
618 the distribution of average Q-scores (top), EMRinger scores (middle), and map–model FSC at the
619 0.5 threshold (bottom), for moderate- (left) and high-resolution (right) cryo-EM datasets. The
620 boxplots indicates medians, interquartile ranges, and whiskers, with individual data points
621 overlaid. Maps were processed using LocSpiral2 under relaxed (LocSpiral2) and exigent
622 (LocSpiral2*) criteria, alongside unprocessed average maps and alternative post-processing
623 methods (cryoTEN, DeepEMhancer, EMReady, EMReady2, and LocScale). Per-map numerical
624 values for Q-scores, EMRinger scores, and FSC metrics are reported in Supplementary Tables S1–
625 S3.

626 **Figure 4 LocQ provides intuitive diagnostics of local structural integrity.** (A) Local quality
627 maps (LocFOM, LocSNR, C, LocQ and LocQ*) computed from independent half-maps of TRP
628 channel (EMD-10418). LocQ and LocQ* refer to the relaxed and exigent criteria. (C) Same plots
629 than in (A) but computed for the human hemoglobin (EMD-31915). (B-D) Half-map slices
630 coloured by LocFOM metric for the channel (left) and hemoglobin (right) highlighting structural
631 inconsistencies between half maps at the used resolution ranges.

632 **Figure 5 LocFOM facilitates validation of map–model agreement and deep learning**
633 **sharpening.** (A-B) Deposited and simulated PDB maps of the TRP channel coloured with
634 LocFOM values. Zoomed regions highlight local phase inconsistencies between the primary map
635 (grey), the LocFOM-coloured map, and the atomic model (green). (C-D) Equivalent analysis for
636 human hemoglobin, showing comparisons between the primary map (grey), the LocFOM-coloured
637 map, the atomic model (green), and the simulated PDB map (yellow).
638 (E-F) Deposited TRP channel map (EMD-10418) coloured with LocFOM values computed by
639 comparison with DeepEMhancer (E) and EMReady2 (F) reconstructions. (G-H) DeepEMhancer

640 and EMReady2 reconstructions of the TRP channel coloured with LocFOM values computed by
641 comparison with the deposited map. **(I-L)** Equivalent LocFOM analyses for human hemoglobin
642 (EMD-31915).

643 **Figure 6 LocAnisotropy analysis of reconstruction anisotropy.** Cryo-EM reconstructions of
644 **(A)** apoferritin (EMD-11638), **(B)** β -galactosidase (EMD-2984), **(C)** influenza hemagglutinin
645 trimer (EMD-38084), and **(D)** PSI-8LHCI (EMD-38086) coloured with voxel-wise
646 LocAnisotropy values. Maps are shown at high- (left) and low-density (right) thresholds to
647 visualize LocAnisotropy values inside and outside the solvent mask. Average LocAnisotropy
648 values computed within and outside the solvent mask are indicated for each dataset.

649 **Figure 7 LocSpiral2 ligand validation of a Spike:Bicycle molecule complex reconstruction.**
650 **(A)** Local quality maps (LocFOM, LocSNR, LocQ) computed from independent half-maps of
651 EMDB-51660. Two views are presented, 90 degrees apart. **(B)** Analysis of
652 reconstruction anisotropy for the same complex. **(C)** Final reconstructed map of the complex is
653 shown at the top, to locate the position of the E4 Bicycle molecule binder. **(D)** Zoom-in of
654 the LocSNR-cloured map for the E4 binder. **(E)** Zoom-in of the LocFOM-coloured map for the
655 E4 binder. **(F)** Zoom-in of the reconstructed map for the E4 binder (coloured in green forest, Spike
656 S1 protein in cyan). **(G)** Zoom-in of the LocSpiral2 map (yellow) of the E4 epitope, with the
657 reconstructed map (grey) for comparison.
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659 **Figures**

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4

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Figure 6

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Figure 7

688 **Tables**

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Maps	Q _{type}	ALL				PROTEIN			
		mean	median	Q ₁	Q ₃	mean	median	Q ₁	Q ₃
Deposited	Q _{backbone}	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.96
	Q _{residue}	0.64	0.86	0.17	0.95	0.88	0.94	0.83	0.96
	Q _{sidechain}	0.81	0.92	0.73	0.96	0.81	0.93	0.72	0.96
EMReady2	Q _{backbone}	0.90	0.91	0.90	0.91	0.90	0.91	0.90	0.91
	Q _{residue}	0.69	0.89	0.77	0.91	0.88	0.90	0.87	0.91
	Q _{sidechain}	0.86	0.90	0.85	0.92	0.86	0.90	0.85	0.92
LocSpiral2	Q _{backbone}	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.97
	Q _{residue}	0.83	0.95	0.86	0.97	0.92	0.96	0.93	0.97
	Q _{sidechain}	0.89	0.96	0.90	0.97	0.89	0.96	0.90	0.97
	Q _{backbone}	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.96
LocSpiral2*	Q _{residue}	0.91	0.95	0.91	0.96	0.92	0.95	0.92	0.96
	Q _{sidechain}	0.89	0.95	0.88	0.96	0.89	0.95	0.88	0.96

693 Table 1

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700 **Supplementary Material**

701 **Local signal to noise ratio (LocSNR)**

702 We estimate the local SNR at frequency ω by the average and difference maps in Eq. (2) as

703
$$\text{LocSNR}_\omega(\mathbf{r}) = \left(\frac{m_{V,\omega}(\mathbf{r})}{m_{D,\omega}(\mathbf{r})} \right)^2 - 1 \quad (26)$$

704 with $m_{V,\omega}(\mathbf{r})$ and $m_{D,\omega}(\mathbf{r})$ the amplitudes of the average and difference maps at frequency ω . In
705 the following, σ^2 indicates variance, power or energy of the signal. Note that the relation between
706 LocSNR and the half map signal to noise ratio (SNR_ω) at frequency ω , is $\text{LocSNR}_\omega =$
707 $\sigma_{V_\omega}^2 / \sigma_{D_\omega}^2 - 1 = \sigma_{S_\omega}^2 / \frac{\sigma_{N_\omega}^2}{2} = 2\text{SNR}_{\text{half},\omega}$, where half maps are given by $V_{1,\omega} = S_\omega + N_{1,\omega}$ and
708 $V_{2,\omega} = S_\omega + N_{2,\omega}$, with S_ω , $N_{1,\omega}$ and $N_{2,\omega}$ true signal and two independent noise realizations at
709 frequency ω respectively. Moreover, we consider unbiased reconstructions, thus, $\sigma_{N_{1,\omega}}^2 = \sigma_{N_{2,\omega}}^2 =$
710 $\sigma_{N_\omega}^2$, then, $\sigma_{V_\omega}^2 = \sigma_{S_\omega}^2 + \sigma_{N_\omega}^2/2$ and $\sigma_{D_\omega}^2 = \sigma_{N_\omega}^2/2$ (pure noise). Consequently, LocSNR_ω
711 calculated from the average and difference maps is two times the SNR of half maps ($\text{SNR}_{\text{half},\omega}$).
712 Therefore, since LocSNR computed from the average and difference maps is twice the
713 corresponding half-map SNR, a natural and physically meaningful quality threshold for LocSNR
714 is 1, corresponding to equal signal and noise power in the reconstructed map. However, in some
715 cases this threshold may be overly restrictive, since local phase differences between half-maps
716 may reduce local signal coherence, thereby increasing the difference map amplitude ($m_{D,\omega}(\mathbf{r})$)
717 beyond the contribution expected from noise alone. Accordingly, $\text{LocSNR} = 1$ represents a
718 conservative quality threshold.

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Figure S1

724 **Supplementary Tables**

Q-SCORE									
MODERATE RESOLUTION									
Map	Resolución	CryoTEN	DeepEMhancer	EMReady2	EMReady	LocScale	Average map	LocSpiral2I	LocSpiral2s
EMD-0004	3.2	0.52	0.47	0.58	0.59	0.53	0.49	0.52	0.53
EMD-0282	3.3	0.63	0.56	0.67	0.68	0.60	0.58	0.63	0.67
EMD-0311	4.2	0.37	0.28	0.41	0.43	0.40	0.34	0.37	0.42
EMD-0520	3.1	0.57	0.52	0.61	0.63	0.52	0.55	0.57	0.62
EMD-0560	3.2	0.63	0.57	0.69	0.70	0.63	0.56	0.65	0.62
EMD-10337	3.6	0.41	0.37	0.49	0.50	0.44	0.39	0.45	0.45
EMD-10350	3.7	0.45	0.37	0.50	0.51	0.47	0.41	0.44	0.43
EMD-10365	3.1	0.64	0.59	0.68	0.69	0.63	0.61	0.63	0.68
EMD-10492	2.9	0.50	0.46	0.57	0.55	0.52	0.50	0.52	0.56
EMD-10649	4.3	0.29	0.23	0.33	0.32	0.34	0.29	0.34	0.35
EMD-10817	3.1	0.64	0.57	0.67	0.68	0.61	0.59	0.61	0.67
EMD-11112	3.8	0.49	0.43	0.53	0.54	0.52	0.43	0.50	0.54
EMD-11557	3.0	0.47	0.43	0.53	0.50	0.52	0.45	0.54	0.54
EMD-11624	4.1	0.26	0.15	0.29	0.27	0.27	0.26	0.26	0.26
HIGH RESOLUTION									
Map	Resolution	CryoTEN	DeepEMhancer	EMReady2	EMReady	LocScale	Average map	LocSpiral2I	LocSpiral2s
EMD-10574	2.2	0.86	0.77	0.85	0.82	0.83	0.80	0.86	0.84
EMD-14429	2.6	0.72	0.64	0.76	0.74	0.71	0.67	0.74	0.74
EMD-14522	2.6	0.75	0.67	0.79	0.78	0.73	0.71	0.76	0.78
EMD-14528	2.5	0.56	0.52	0.59	0.56	0.54	0.56	0.57	0.57
EMD-16433	2.5	0.76	0.71	0.77	0.75	0.76	0.75	0.78	0.76
EMD-17298	2.0	0.83	0.72	0.86	0.84	0.83	0.78	0.85	0.84
EMD-17583	2.5	0.76	0.67	0.81	0.80	0.74	0.71	0.80	0.80
EMD-23786	2.5	0.73	0.64	0.80	0.80	0.74	0.65	0.79	0.80
EMD-26957	2.0	0.87	0.75	0.82	0.76	0.85	0.83	0.84	0.83
EMD-28147	2.2	0.82	0.74	0.85	0.83	0.80	0.78	0.85	0.84
EMD-31911	2.3	0.73	0.68	0.79	0.75	0.74	0.72	0.77	0.79
EMD-34368	2.5	0.79	0.71	0.82	0.82	0.76	0.74	0.80	0.80
EMD-35453	2.5	0.78	0.72	0.83	0.82	0.77	0.73	0.81	0.81
EMD-36468	2.6	0.56	0.49	0.60	0.60	0.54	0.53	0.57	0.58
EMD-39867	2.3	0.72	0.63	0.77	0.78	0.72	0.66	0.76	0.75

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Table S1

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EMRINGER SCORE									
MODERATE RESOLUTION									
Map	Resolution	CryoTEN	DeepEMhancer	EMReady2	EMReady	LocScale	Average map	LocSpiral2l	LocSpiral2s
EMD-0004	3.2	2.69	2.73	3.04	2.93	2.66	2.58	2.95	2.97
EMD-0282	3.3	3.94	3.87	4.04	4.13	4.12	3.87	4.20	4.12
EMD-0311	4.2	0.84	0.44	1.39	1.46	1.04	-0.075	1.15	1.09
EMD-0520	3.1	3.38	3.25	3.19	3.52	3.55	3.13	3.24	3.27
EMD-0560	3.2	3.77	3.65	4.05	4.01	4.30	3.35	3.89	3.81
EMD-10337	3.6	0.85	0.72	0.96	0.74	1.06	0.59	1.31	1.31
EMD-10350	3.7	1.01	1.00	0.96	1.41	1.12	0.83	1.23	1.15
EMD-10365	3.1	2.49	3.25	2.79	3.04	3.43	3.07	2.67	2.79
EMD-10492	2.9	1.89	2.40	2.62	2.38	2.37	2.38	2.35	2.48
EMD-10649	4.3	0.47	0.47	0.91	0.42	0.80	-0.84	1.02	0.86
EMD-10817	3.1	4.18	4.35	4.17	4.54	4.31	3.71	3.96	4.11
EMD-11112	3.8	1.40	1.40	1.56	1.20	1.51	0.58	1.56	1.74
EMD-11557	3.0	3.73	3.40	4.27	4.06	3.61	2.50	4.22	4.34
EMD-11624	4.1	0.16	0.12	0.26	0.36	0.26	-0.53	0.57	0.39
HIGH RESOLUTION									
Map	Resolution	CryoTEN	DeepEMhancer	EMReady2	EMReady	LocScale	Average map	LocSpiral2l	LocSpiral2s
EMD-10574	2.2	6.90	6.90	7.21	7.00	7.37	7.13	7.16	7.09
EMD-14429	2.6	3.50	3.31	3.88	3.41	4.06	3.50	3.68	3.84
EMD-14522	2.6	5.63	5.35	5.95	6.10	5.56	5.34	5.88	5.96
EMD-14528	2.5	1.92	2.24	2.26	2.26	2.28	1.98	1.97	1.90
EMD-16433	2.5	4.22	3.73	3.96	4.51	4.49	4.68	4.73	4.11
EMD-17298	2.0	5.56	5.02	5.82	5.79	6.22	5.55	6.11	5.72
EMD-17583	2.5	4.99	4.74	4.94	4.90	5.14	4.75	4.98	5.05
EMD-23786	2.5	4.72	4.61	5.08	5.16	5.53	4.79	5.10	5.07
EMD-26957	2.0	5.87	5.43	6.28	5.99	6.48	5.84	6.38	6.16
EMD-28147	2.2	4.63	4.57	4.70	5.75	5.15	5.21	5.57	5.53
EMD-31911	2.3	4.14	4.63	4.83	4.23	4.81	4.15	4.98	4.96
EMD-34368	2.5	4.12	4.08	4.14	4.40	4.12	3.81	4.01	3.98
EMD-35453	2.5	4.48	4.32	4.61	4.72	4.70	4.59	4.31	4.35
EMD-36468	2.6	2.91	2.87	3.34	3.01	2.75	3.21	2.54	2.61
EMD-39867	2.3	3.95	3.84	4.29	4.13	4.43	3.97	4.48	4.33

Table S2

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D FSC MODEL 05																	
MODERATE RESOLUTION																	
Map	Resolution	CryoTEN		DeepEMhancer		EMReady2		EMReady		LocScale		Average map		LocSpiral2l		LocSpiral2s	
		Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask
EMD-0004	3.2	3.44	3.47	3.63	3.70	3.08	3.08	2.94	2.94	3.62	3.63	3.66	6.18	3.42	3.42	3.33	3.33
EMD-0282	3.3	3.22	3.26	3.39	3.42	2.77	2.77	2.58	2.58	3.30	3.33	3.43	4.35	3.09	3.12	2.87	2.87
EMD-0311	4.2	4.25	4.25	6.51	6.62	4.13	4.13	4.14	4.14	4.29	4.28	4.45	6.50	4.27	4.28	4.18	4.13
EMD-0520	3.1	3.23	3.25	3.40	3.40	3.01	3.01	2.84	2.86	3.37	3.39	3.40	4.24	3.18	3.2	3.01	3.01
EMD-0560	3.2	3.27	3.27	3.40	3.40	2.76	2.76	2.39	2.39	3.29	3.28	3.32	3.69	3.12	3.12	3.23	3.23
EMD-10337	3.6	4.34	4.36	4.43	4.43	4.11	4.11	4.04	4.05	4.38	4.39	4.48	6.44	4.32	4.32	4.29	4.29
EMD-10350	3.7	4.02	4.02	4.16	4.16	3.83	3.84	3.76	3.76	4.08	4.07	4.08	6.98	4.02	4.02	4.02	4.02
EMD-10365	3.1	3.08	3.34	3.25	3.51	2.75	2.84	2.42	2.78	3.11	3.15	3.33	3.74	3.00	3.18	2.82	2.96
EMD-10492	2.9	3.42	3.42	3.61	3.61	3.07	3.07	3.17	3.17	3.49	3.49	3.49	3.97	3.37	3.37	3.07	3.07
EMD-10649	4.3	4.60	4.59	6.67	6.67	4.59	4.60	4.74	4.74	4.57	4.58	4.60	6.42	4.54	4.55	4.59	4.59
EMD-10817	3.1	3.13	3.13	3.38	3.39	2.83	2.83	2.76	2.75	3.32	3.33	3.38	3.80	3.13	3.13	2.86	2.86
EMD-11112	3.8	3.95	3.95	3.98	3.98	3.88	3.88	3.87	3.87	4.00	4.00	4.02	4.12	3.92	3.93	3.88	3.88
EMD-11557	3.0	3.72	3.73	4.02	4.02	3.42	3.45	3.45	3.46	3.71	3.74	3.45	3.74	3.22	3.22	3.22	3.22
EMD-11624	4.1	6.52	6.53	7.18	7.18	6.36	6.36	6.46	6.47	7.65	6.63	6.54	6.70	6.49	6.49	6.49	6.49
HIGH RESOLUTION																	
Map	Resolution	CryoTEN		DeepEMhancer		EMReady2		EMReady		LocScale		Average map		LocSpiral2l		LocSpiral2s	
		Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask	Mask	Unmask
EMD-10574	2.2	1.75	1.75	2.59	2.59	1.42	1.42	1.57	1.57	1.89	1.89	2.26	2.83	1.59	1.59	1.61	1.62
EMD-14429	2.6	2.62	2.62	3.06	3.06	2.10	2.11	2.09	2.09	2.67	2.69	2.77	3.31	2.29	2.29	2.28	2.28
EMD-14522	2.6	3.19	3.19	3.37	3.36	3.14	3.14	3.17	3.17	3.26	3.19	3.19	3.22	11.33	11.39	3.16	3.16
EMD-14528	2.5	3.37	3.37	3.40	3.40	3.00	3.00	3.11	3.11	3.35	3.57	3.40	3.77	3.13	3.13	3.13	3.13
EMD-16433	2.5	2.30	2.31	2.84	2.83	2.05	2.05	2.06	2.06	2.49	2.49	2.58	3.09	2.31	2.31	2.32	2.32
EMD-17298	2.0	1.83	1.87	2.84	2.83	1.48	1.48	1.61	1.61	2.01	2.01	2.20	2.42	1.75	1.75	1.75	1.75
EMD-17583	2.5	2.37	2.41	2.98	2.98	1.74	1.73	1.70	1.70	2.49	2.50	2.62	3.02	1.98	1.98	1.98	1.99
EMD-23786	2.5	2.66	2.66	3.16	3.16	1.76	1.76	1.73	1.73	2.54	2.54	2.66	3.19	2.00	2.00	2.03	2.03
EMD-26957	2.0	1.76	1.84	2.61	2.60	1.43	1.46	1.59	1.60	1.80	1.82	2.13	2.86	1.55	1.55	1.57	1.57
EMD-28147	2.2	2.07	2.09	2.63	2.62	1.47	1.47	1.57	1.59	2.16	2.17	2.39	2.62	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
EMD-31911	2.3	2.49	2.49	2.76	2.77	1.79	1.79	1.89	1.89	2.26	2.27	2.52	2.88	1.99	1.99	1.9	1.9
EMD-34368	2.5	2.23	2.23	2.86	2.86	1.81	1.82	1.70	1.71	2.46	2.47	2.72	3.17	1.98	1.99	1.98	1.99
EMD-35453	2.5	2.36	2.37	2.82	2.82	1.83	1.83	1.73	1.73	2.45	2.45	2.73	3.15	2.04	2.04	2.04	2.04
EMD-36468	2.6	3.24	3.24	3.40	3.40	2.99	2.99	2.73	2.73	3.35	3.40	3.43	3.90	3.21	3.21	3.2	3.2
EMD-39867	2.3	2.57	2.59	3.08	3.08	1.90	1.90	1.84	1.84	2.61	2.61	2.74	3.24	2.16	2.17	2.18	2.18

Table S3

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